

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE REVENUES OF LARGE PUBLIC HOSPITALS IN BULGARIA

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Abstract

Public enterprises play an important role in the economic and social life of the country. They are legal entities that are created and managed in the interest of citizens and society in order to achieve maximum value for society through efficient allocation of resources. A proportion of public companies is entrusted with public functions or the performance of public services, which means that they contribute a benefit to society that cannot always be measured in financial terms.

State medical institutions in Bulgaria are commercial companies in the sense of the Commercial Law and public enterprises in the sense of the Law on Public Enterprises, but the functions they perform are socially oriented, and their main activity is the provision of medical services to the population, not the implementation of the most profitable financial result for the company.

Almost all state-owned public enterprises report the immediate and negative impact of the global COVID-19 pandemic and the long-term consequences of its action, which led to a drastic decline in services provided and sales, and the effect of this on the financial statements for 2020 is a reduction of revenues, reported operating losses and a reduction in cash inflow.

Keywords: public enterprises, state medical facilities for hospital care, revenue analysis, university hospitals, commercial companies

Introduction:

In most countries, state regulation in the management of public finances for health care is leading, despite trends towards greater liberalization of the health services market and the introduction of competition. [5]

Public enterprises play an important role in the economic and social life of the country. They are legal entities that are created and managed in the interest of citizens and society in order to achieve maximum value for society through efficient allocation of resources. A proportion of public companies are entrusted with public functions or the performance of public services, which means that they contribute a benefit to society that cannot always be measured in financial terms. Although public enterprises in Bulgaria are managed in the same way as private companies, and the provisions of the Commercial Law apply equally to both private and public companies, with the adoption of the Law on Public Enterprises and the regulations for its implementation, only the legal framework was created for the improvement of corporate governance, the great challenge for its implementation in practice lies ahead. The goal that the state sets for itself with the launched reform is to largely follow the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Guidelines for corporate governance of state-owned enterprises,

which provide the state as owner and state-owned enterprises a predictable framework, so that the role of the owner of the state to be clearly separated from its other functions. [1]

State medical institutions (a medical institution whose capital is more than 50 percent owned by the state), according to §1, item 2 of the additional provisions of the Law on Medical Institutions) are commercial companies within the meaning of the Commercial Law (CL) and public enterprises within the meaning of the Law on Public Enterprises (LPE), but the functions they perform are socially oriented, and their main activity is the provision of medical services to the population, and not the realization of the most advantageous financial result for the company. State medical facilities are an integral part of the national health service, as their aim is not to carry out economic activity, but to provide health services, on the principle of solidarity, being financed by a public fund, through the social security system. In practice, medical institutions are obliged to carry out activities for the benefit of society, with all the accompanying legal restrictions, while at the same time functioning as commercial companies, with all the resulting obligations.

The norms of the Law on Public Enterprises and the Regulations for Application of the Law on Public Enterprises are difficult to apply in relation to public

enterprises whose activity is not purely economic in nature, and in particular public enterprises - state medical institutions. [7]

The purpose of the present study is to perform a comparative analysis of the revenues of public hospitals for hospital care categorized as "large" in Bulgaria.

Methodology:

The following research methods were used: documentary method - financial and accounting reports of the group of medical facilities for hospital care, website of the Agency for Public Enterprises and Control, economic analysis, comparative analysis, mathematical and statistical method, graphic analysis – to visualize the results obtained.

The consolidated financial statements in the presented research are a summary of the financial information provided by the relevant public enterprises in the Annual Financial Statements for the period 2019-2021. [1,2,3]

Included are the state-owned enterprises established on the basis of Art. 62, para. 3 of the Commercial Law, which states that "State enterprises that are not commercial companies may be established by law" [4].

Main part:

Brief presentation of the public medical facilities included in the study categorized as "large" - university hospitals:

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment "St. Ivan Rilski" JSC, Sofia - All structural units have modern high-quality equipment, exceeding the requirements for the third level of implementation of the established medical standards (the highest), on which UMHAT "St. Ivan Rilski" JSC.

The medical facility has developed, implemented and maintains a Quality Management System that meets the requirements of the international standard ISO 9001:2008 from 2009, standard ISO 9001:2015 from 2021.

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment "Dr. Georgi Stranski" JSC, Pleven was established more than 145 years ago and is the largest hospital care facility in Northern Bulgaria. Its main activities include diagnosis and treatment of diseases in all profiles of medical specialties; treatment of emergency conditions; highly specialized research and consultation of patients from other medical institutions. The hospital is one of the established centers included in the organ and tissue donation program for transplantation. It is a center for university education and provides modern training opportunities for students, trainee doctors, residents and health care professionals.

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment "St. Marina" JSC, Varna is the largest diagnostic-treatment and advisory university hospital complex in North-Eastern Bulgaria, serving a population from all over the country, which has over 1,300 beds, the most modern equipment and highly qualified personnel - university professors, national and regional consultants.

In 2021, the activity of the medical facility under the contract with the National Health Insurance Fund

was implemented in strict compliance with the fixed monthly volumes of activity. The management of UMHAT "Sveta Marina" JSC - Varna strives for strict compliance throughout the scope of its activities with the Horizontal policies of the European Union, regarding equality, non-discrimination and sustainable development.

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment "Alexandrovska" JSC, Sofia is the oldest hospital and one of the largest in the country. With its establishment in 1879 under the name Sofia First Class Hospital, it received the status and functions of a national medical institution. Today UMHAT "Alexandrovska" JSC is a leading national university and medical center in multi-disciplinary medical, transplant, dispensary, educational and research activities.

With its multi-disciplinary spectrum, the hospital is the largest base for development, clinical testing and application of modern highly effective methods and technologies for diagnosis and treatment.

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment and Emergency Medicine "N.I.Pirogov" JSC, Sofia is the largest hospital in the Republic of Bulgaria for emergency and disaster medicine. The medical facility has structures that have no analogues in the country: departments of pediatric urology, pediatric toxicology, pediatric burn and plastic surgery, pediatric abdominal surgery, pediatric thoracic surgery, surgery of the newborn and congenital anomalies, pediatric neurosurgery, purulent clinic - septic surgery.

The multi-specialty emergency department maintains round-the-clock security with teams separately for each specialty that the hospital works on and that is included in the authorization to carry out medical activity.

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment "St. Georgi" JSC, Plovdiv is the main center for emergency services for patients from the city and the regions of southern Bulgaria. In 2000, it was converted into a commercial company. It is one of the established centers included in the organ and tissue donation program for transplantation. It has medical equipment and technology from the most renowned companies, which is used in the diagnostic-treatment and educational process.

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment "Prof. Dr. Alexander Chirkov" ("St. Ekaterina") JSC, Sofia occupies a leading position among hospitals, cardiology and cardiac surgery centers in Bulgaria, the Balkans and the European Union. It is the only hospital in Bulgaria where heart transplants are routinely performed. It performs the largest volume and difficulty of modern vascular-surgical interventions.

This is the only hospital in Bulgaria with a license for heart transplants. The hospital operates in conditions of excellent material and technical support, which allows the provision of high-tech medical assistance, including heart transplants. The personnel stability of the hospital, expressed in the high loyalty of leading medical specialists, their ability to extremely effectively transfer their knowledge, skills and experience to younger staff.

University Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment "Lozenets" JSC, Sofia - The hospital was established by Decision No. 693/21.11.2019 of the Council of Ministers, by which Lozenets Hospital was transformed into a single-member joint-stock company with state participation in the capital under the name MHAT "Lozenets" JSC.

In recent years, UMHAT "Lozenets", in addition to developing the main medical fields, specializes in modern and leading diagnostic and treatment activities such as: imaging diagnostics, invasive cardiology, endoscopic surgery, etc. It has become a medical institution commensurate with European and world standards both in terms of material base and in terms of organization and efficiency of the diagnostic and treatment activity. This made it possible to implement many innovations in medical practice and make the hospital a model for the development of other hospitals in the country.

In 2021, cash receipts and payments were synchronized to a much better degree. The prepared finan-

cial report for the year 2021 of the hospital as a commercial company is the second and the data is compared with the previous year 2020. [3]

The property provided by the state to the state-owned enterprises does not form capital to serve as collateral for their creditors (ie the property provided to them is not divided into a number of units/shares with a fixed nominal value). Some of them apply a specific regulatory framework, which distinguishes them both from commercial companies and from each other. Nevertheless, they are also registered in the commercial register and apply the provisions of the Accounting Act. For this reason and in order to obtain a more complete and clear picture of the state's participation in the economic life of the country, the study includes the financial results of their activity, in an analogous way to commercial companies, but the performance of the "big" state enterprises in Art. 62, para. 3 of the Commercial Law does not contain all financial and economic indicators.

Figure 1. Income statement, thousand BGN

Sources: Agency for Public Enterprises and Control, Annual Summary Reports on State Public Enterprises for 2019, 2020 and 2021

For UMHAT "St. Ivan Rilski" JSC, Sofia in 2021, the company's total revenues increased by BGN 25,370 thousand (33.4% compared to 2019). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 25,338 thousand (30.4%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reported a net profit of BGN 1,449,000, and as of 2019, BGN 1,078,000, i.e. with an increase of BGN 371 thousand – 34.4%.

For UMHAT "Dr. Georgi Stranski" JSC, Pleven in 2021, the company's total revenues increased by BGN 26,018 thousand (33.1% compared to 2019). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 25,707 thousand (32.7%). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 25,707 thousand (32.7%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reports a net loss in the amount of (-6,029) thousand BGN, and as of 2019 (-1,103) thousand BGN, i.e. with an increase of (-4,926) thousand BGN.

For UMHAT "St. Marina" JSC, Varna in 2021, the company's total revenues increased by BGN 40,446 thousand (33.6% compared to 2019). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 40,615 thousand (34.1%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reported a net profit of BGN 5,986 thousand, and as of 2019, BGN 3,063 thousand, i.e. with an increase of BGN 2,923 thousand – 95.4%.

For UMHAT "Alexandrovska" JSC, Sofia in 2021, the company's total revenues increased by BGN 102,601 thousand (47.4% compared to 2019). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 32,925 thousand (47.3%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reports a net loss in the amount of (-2,412) thousand BGN, and as of 2019 (-6,047) thousand BGN, i.e. with a reduction in the net loss of BGN 3,635 thousand.

For UMHATEM "N.I.Pirogov" JSC, Sofia in 2021, the company's total revenues increased by BGN 38,849 thousand (43.6% compared to 2019). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 38,972 thousand (43.8%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reports a net profit in the amount of BGN 2,889 thousand, while as of 2019, a net loss in the amount of (-108) thousand BGN, i.e. with an increase in net profit of BGN 2,997 thousand.

UMHAT "St. Georgi" JSC, Plovdiv presents the best results in the income statement. In 2021, the company's total revenues increased by BGN 57,925 thousand (37.7% compared to 2019). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 38,972 thousand (43.8%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reported a net profit of BGN 9,336,000, and as of 2019, BGN 4,190,000, i.e. with an increase of BGN 5,146 thousand – 122.8%.

For UMHAT "Prof. Dr. Alexander Chirkov" JSC, Sofia in 2021, the company's total revenues increased by BGN 2,905 thousand (8.6% compared to 2019). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 2,925 thousand (8.7%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reports a net profit in the amount of BGN 108 thousand, as of 2019 it reports a net profit in the amount of (-2,283) thousand BGN, i.e. with an increase of BGN 2,391 thousand.

For UMHAT "Lozenets" JSC, Sofia in 2021, cash receipts and payments are synchronized to a very good

extent. The prepared financial statement for this year of the hospital as a commercial company is the second and the data is compared with 2020. The company's total revenues increased in 2021 by BGN 10,331 thousand (32.4% compared to 2020). Revenues from operating activities increased by BGN 10,336 thousand (32.4%). As of 31.12.2021, the hospital reports a net loss in the amount of (-18,617) thousand BGN, as of 2020 (-21,241) thousand BGN, i.e. with a reduction in the net loss of BGN 2,624 thousand.

Given the state of emergency and the situation in the country, the financial indicators of the hospitals cannot be an indicator of the real opportunities for activity, since in the conditions of an epidemic situation, the reception and treatment of planned patients was stopped for a certain period at the beginning.

The Council of Ministers adopted a Decree approving additional costs and transfers under the budget of the Ministry of Health for 2021 in the amount of BGN 61,011,200. [3]

The adoption of the draft Decree is necessary due to the extension of the period of the emergency epidemic situation until 31.03.2022 and the need to ensure the sustainability of the measure for providing additional remuneration to the medical and non-medical personnel directly engaged in the implementation of the activities related to the measures for the prevention and fight against COVID-19.

The provision of a monthly additional remuneration for front-line medics in the amount of BGN 1,000 net is an effective and sustainable measure to deal with the situation with the spread of COVID-19 and an essential factor for the motivation of medical personnel [6]

Conclusions:

1. State medical institutions are an integral part of the national health care, as their goal is not to carry out economic activity, but to provide health services, on the principle of solidarity, being financed by a public fund, through the social security system.

2. At the public university multi-profile hospitals for active treatment categorized as "large" in the Republic of Bulgaria UMBAL "St. Marina" EAD, Varna in 2021 reports a net profit with an increase of 95.4%, and UMBAL "St. Georgi" EAD, Plovdiv with an increase of 122.8% compared to 2019.

3. Almost all state-owned public enterprises report the immediate and negative impact of the global pandemic of COVID-19 and the long-term consequences of its action, which led to difficulties in the business and economic activity of public enterprises, a drastic drop in the services provided and sales, with the effect of this on the 2020 financial statements being a reduction in revenue, reported operating losses and a reduction in cash inflow.

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